

Prandtl-Tomlinson model demonstrator made with LEGO™ pieces

Additional materials:

- cylindrical magnets < 4.8 mm in diameter;
- large fridge-type magnet;
- weak/small spring or a Newton-meter;
- and thread or string.

Optional materials are blu-tac or double-sided tape to assist in putting the magnets in place or fixing the demonstrator in place on a table. The minimum estimated number of magnets needed is 38 (20 in the red pieces and 18 in the purple pieces). Shorter magnets may be more desirable as they allow you to fine-tune the magnetic strength of the model. If the stick-slip phenomenon isn't observed in the completed model, disassemble the surface pieces and adjust the number of magnets. We found good results using 67 neodymium (N52) magnets of 3mm in diameter and 1mm tall, with carrying capacity of 0.126 kg. We used 8 per red piece and 3 per purple piece.

Use

On a flat surface use a thin amount of blu-tac or double-sided tape to fix the model in place, if desired. During assembly, tie some string around the middle of the slider bar, ensuring to loop around the whole structure. At the end of the string attach the spring and another small amount of string (or a loop to attach a Newton-meter). Like this:

Then add a large fridge-type magnet to the tip using blu-tac or double-sided tape.

The parts list comes with additional round 2x2 white plates and a shorter grey axle piece to help adjust height depending on magnet size.

Pulling the slider across the surface and examining the length of the spring will give a good indicator of changes in friction. The demonstrator will also show classic tribological stick-slip behaviour.

Tweaks

If you wish to tweak the model, simply download and install BrickLink.com's free design program [Studio](#). Then you can use this program to open the design file for this model: "PrandtlTomlinsonModel.io".

Parts list

To order this model please see “OrderingLEGO.pdf”.

List as .csv file: “PTModel.csv”.

Image	Description	Item No (& alternate Item Nos)	Colour	Qty
	Brick 1 x 1	3005 30071 35382 3005f1 3005f2 3005f3	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Brick 1 x 2 with Axle Hole	31493 32064 32064b	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Technic, Brick 1 x 2 with Hole	3700	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Slope 45 2 x 1	3040 6270 35281	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Brick 1 x 3 with Holes	5565	Bright Red or Red	2
	Brick 1 x 4	3010 6146	Bright Red or Red	1
	Brick 1 x 4	3010 6146	Medium Lilac or Dark Purple	9
	Brick 1 x 6	3009 3009f1 3009f2 3009f3 30611	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Brick 2 x 2 Corner	2357	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Brick 2 x 4	3001 3001f 3556 15589 54534 72841	Bright Red or Red	4
	Brick 2 x 4	3001 3001f 3556 15589 54534 72841	Bright Blue or Blue	5
	Brick, Round 2 x 2 with Axle Hole	3941	White	1
	Plate 1 x 6	3666	Medium Azure	4
	Plate 1 x 8	3460	Black	1

	Plate 1 x 8	3460			Medium Azure	6
	Plate 1 x 12	60479			Black	2
	Wedge, Plate 2 x 2 Cut Corner	26601			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	12
	Plate 2 x 6	3795			Black	1
	Plate 2 x 6	3795			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 2 x 8	3034			Medium Azure	3
	Plate 6 x 14	3456			Black	2
	Plate 8 x 8	41539	42534		Black	2
	Plate 8 x 16	92438			Black	3
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Axle Hole	4032			White	5
	Tile 1 x 2	3069 35386 54285	3069b 37293 88630	30070 45880 113482	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Tile 1 x 4	2431 91143	35371 100687	75703 112418	Bright Red or Red	1
	Tile 1 x 4	2431 91143	35371 100687	75703 112418	Medium Lilac or Dark Purple	9
	Tile 2 x 2	3068 3068b 1136	63327 78814	88409 113493	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Tile 2 x 4	87079	38879	71150	Bright Red or Red	4
	Tile 2 x 4	87079	38879	71150	Bright Blue or Blue	5

	Tile 2 x 6	69729		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Tile, Round Corner 2 x 2 Macaroni	27925 113485	67124 78560	White	19
	Tile, Round 2 x 2 with Hole	15535		White	1
	Hinge Brick 1 x 2 Top Plate	3938		Black	6
	Hinge Brick 1 x 2 Base	3937		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Technic, Pin with Short Friction Ridges	61332	2780	Black	2
	Technic, Axle and Pin Connector Angled	42127	32013	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Axle 1L with Pin with Friction Ridges	43093		Bright Blue or Blue	2
	Technic, Pin with Bar and Tow Ball, 3L	80477		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Axle and Pin Connector Perpendicular 3L with Center Pin Hole	42142	32184	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 5	32316	41616	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Plate 1 x 5 with Smooth Ends, 4 Studs and Center Axle Hole	50029	32124	Bright Blue or Blue	2
	Technic, Axle 4L with Stop	87083		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Technic, Axle 5L with Stop	15462		Reddish Brown	3
	Technic, Axle 32L	13927	50450	Black	2